

Strengthening Soil: Harnessing Date Palm Leaf Fibers for Sustainable Reinforcement

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Abstract:

The soil reinforcement considered to be one of the main recent techniques used for the improvement of soft soil mechanical properties. Various works of investigation have been done based on using metal and geosynthetics composite materials. The increasing uses of natural material fibers, mats and shredded pieces are encouraging the investigation for utilization of date palm leaves fiber. The date palm leaves fibers are available in large quantity in many countries' worldwide and in Gulf countries in particular. This paper deals with the study of using the date palm leaves fiber as a reinforcement for Nizwa cohesive soil and investigate the influence of randomly distributed fiber on compaction and compressive strength characteristics of the reinforced soil.

Keywords: Palm leaf fibers, Soil Stabilization, Nizwa, Index properties

1.INTRODUCTION

Soil stabilization is essential for enhancing the load-bearing capacity, reducing shrink-swell potential, and improving the overall durability of soil, thereby ensuring the stability and longevity of infrastructure such as roads, buildings, and embankments. For mitigating issues like soil erosion and increasing resistance to weathering and freeze-thaw cycles, soil stabilization techniques play a critical role in preventing structural failures and minimizing maintenance costs. Moreover, it facilitates the use of locally available, marginal soils, promoting cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability (Zhang et al., 2010; George et al., 2021).

In literature, various stabilization techniques like geosynthetics, fibers, and additives (such as cement, lime, fly ash, and bitumen) have been explored to enhance the bearing capacity of subgrade soils (Basha et al., 2005; Fannin et al., 1996; Gray et., 1983; Shukla, 2002). Among these, geosynthetics stand out as the most prevalent and widely favoured solution for soil stabilization (Hausman, 1987; Fannin et., 1996; Giroud et., 2004; Kayadelen et al., 2018; Altay et al., 2019; Negi et., 2019; Altay et al., 2021; Altay et al., 2021).

Soil reinforcement using natural fibers and plant leaves has been a well-established practice since ancient times, aimed at enhancing the properties of soft soils (Marandi et al., 2008). A wide range of natural fibers such as bamboo fiber, date palm leaf fiber, coconut fiber, and jute fiber have been identified as effective reinforcements for soft soil improvement. These fibers are particularly noted for their ability to enhance compressive strength and compaction characteristics, which are critical parameters in soil mechanical properties improvement (Zafar et al., 2023; Ghasemi Nezhad et al., 2023)

Recent studies have further underscored the effectiveness of natural fibers in soil reinforcement. Sadikon et al., (2022) demonstrated the significant improvement in soil shear strength and compressive strength when reinforced with coconut and jute fibers. Similarly, research by Bhattacharyya et al. (2009) highlighted the environmental and economic benefits of using locally available natural fibers for soil stabilization.

In this study, date palm leaf fiber is utilized as a natural reinforcement material for improving the properties of local cohesive soil from Nizwa city, Sultanate of Oman. This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of date palm leaf fiber in enhancing the mechanical properties of the soil, particularly its compressive strength and compaction characteristics. By focusing on locally sourced materials, this study not only addresses soil stabilization but also promotes sustainable and eco-friendly construction practices in the region.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Soil

The soil used in this study is a fine-grained cohesive soil selected from the Ghobrate Nizwa area in Nizwa city, located approximately 140 km southeast of Muscat, Oman. Samples were collected from a depth of 0.5 to 1.0 meters below the ground surface, which is the probable zone affected by weathering. This depth was chosen to ensure the soil used was representative of the typical conditions encountered in the region.

Water

Potable water was utilized for all experimental procedures to maintain consistency and ensure the results were not influenced by water quality variations.

Date Palm Leaf Fiber

Date palm leaf fibers were sourced locally, where they are typically considered solid waste. The preparation of these fibers involved oven-drying the leaves at a temperature of 60-70°C for 24 hours. After drying, the leaves were chopped into fiber-like shapes, measuring 5-10 mm in length and 2-3 mm in diameter. This method of preparation ensures uniformity in fiber dimensions, which is crucial for consistent reinforcement results (AL-Oqla, 2020).

Preparation of Reinforced Soil Specimens and Testing

To prepare the fiber-reinforced soil specimens, the soil was first thoroughly mixed with the specified fiber content. The fiber contents used were 0%, 0.5%, 1.0%, and 2.0% by dry weight of the soil. Following the fiber addition, the recommended amount of water was added to achieve a uniform mix. The mixing process was critical to ensure an even distribution of fibers throughout the soil matrix (Alhakim et al., 2023).

The soil-fiber mixture was then compacted in a cylindrical mold with a diameter of 102 mm and a height of 105 mm. The compaction was performed in five equal layers using the modified AASHTO compactive energy method. This compaction technique is widely recognized for its effectiveness in simulating field conditions (ASTM D698, 2012).

For each fiber content, five molds were compacted at various water contents to determine the compaction characteristics. After compaction, the reinforced soil specimens were extruded from the molds and subjected to unconfined compressive strength (UCS) testing to failure. This testing was essential to evaluate the improvement in compressive strength due to the addition of date palm leaf fibers (KHRISSI, 2024).

Figure 1 illustrates a sample of the prepared date palm leaf fibers, and Figure 2 shows a schematic section of a date palm leaf fiber reinforced soil specimen.

Figure 1- Date palm leaves fibers

Figure 2- Schematic section in soil-fiber specimen

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Index Properties of the Soil

The index properties of the soil used in this study are summarized in Table 1. According to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), the soil is classified as Silt with Low Plasticity (ML), and as A-4 according to the AASHTO classification system. The grain size distribution curve for the soil is illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 1- Index properties of soil

Characteristic	value
Liquid limit, %	39
Plastic Limit, %	27
Plasticity Index, %	12
Specific gravity of solid	2.68
Finer than #200 sieve, %	55
Clay content, %	12
Maximum dry unit weight, kN/m ³	18.45
Optimum moisture content, %	12.5
Sulphate content, %	0.003
Organic matters, %	0.35
Unified Classification	ML
AASHTO Classification	A-4

The compaction characteristics of soil reinforced with varying fiber contents are presented in Figure 5. The overall behavior remains consistent across different reinforcement percentages. It is observed that the increase in dry unit weight on the dry side of the optimum moisture content is more pronounced than the decrease on the wet side. This indicates that reinforced soil on the dry side is more sensitive to water content changes compared to the wet side.

Figure 6 shows the effect of fiber content on the maximum unit weight, revealing a gradual decrease in maximum unit weight with increasing fiber content. This reduction is attributed to the lower specific gravity of the fibers compared to soil solids. Figure 7 illustrates the impact of fiber content on the optimum moisture content, indicating an increase in optimum moisture content with higher fiber content. This is due to the high-water absorption capacity of date palm leaf fibers, reported to be around 224% by Ghasemi Nezhad et., (2023)

Figure 5- Compaction characteristics of fiber reinforced soil for various fiber content.

Figure 6- Effect of fiber content on the maximum dry unit weight.

Figure 7- Effect of fiber content on the optimum moisture content of reinforced soil

Strength characteristics

Figure 8 depicts the relationship between unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and moisture content for reinforced soil with various fiber contents. The compressive strength increases with moisture content up to a certain point, after which it declines as moisture content continues to rise. This trend is consistent across different fiber contents and mirrors the behavior observed in dry unit weight versus moisture content relationships.

The effect of fiber content on the optimum water content that produces the maximum compressive strength is also shown in Figure 8. It is evident that the optimum water content increases with fiber content up to 0.5%, beyond which it begins to decrease. This indicates that less water is needed to achieve maximum strength in soil with higher fiber content.

Figure 9 highlights the effect of fiber content on the compressive strength of reinforced soil. The compressive strength increases with fiber content, with a more significant rate of increase observed at lower fiber percentages (up to 0.5%). This increase in strength can be attributed to the friction between soil particles and the fiber surface area, coupled with the relatively high tensile strength of date palm leaf fibers. The interaction between the fiber surface and soil particles creates an indirect binding force, effectively adding cohesion to the soil. Additionally, the high tensile strength of the fibers enhances frictional resistance, contributing to higher system failure resistance. These factors collectively result in an increase in the compressive strength of the reinforced soil (AL-Oqla, 2020).

Figure 8- Strength characteristics of reinforced soil for various fiber content

Figure 9- Effect of fiber content on the maximum compressive strength of reinforced soil

Soil reinforcement Application

Incorporating date palm leaf fibers as soil reinforcement material in highway construction not only enhances the mechanical properties of the subgrade but also provides an environmentally friendly solution to solid waste management. This approach aligns with the principles of sustainable development and waste minimization. For instance, consider a highway subgrade project where a 1.0 km long and 18 m wide section (comprising three lanes and shoulders) is reinforced using soil-date palm leaf fiber composite. The subgrade consists of two layers, each 250 mm thick. Research indicates that soil reinforced with 2.0% date palm leaf fiber achieves a maximum dry unit weight of 18.4 kN/m³ (Chkala et al., 2024).

Given these parameters, the total volume of the subgrade layers is calculated to be 9,000 m³. To achieve the optimal reinforcement, approximately 322 tons of date palm leaf fibers are required. This utilization of agricultural waste significantly mitigates the environmental impact of solid waste disposal, highlighting the dual benefits of structural enhancement and environmental conservation (Ghasemi et al., 2023). By diverting date palm leaf fibers from waste streams into construction materials, this practice exemplifies an effective strategy for waste valorization, aligning with contemporary environmental protection goals and promoting the use of sustainable materials in infrastructure projects.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study conducted on using date palm leaf fibers as a soil reinforcement material has yielded significant insights into its potential benefits and effects on soil properties. The following conclusions can be drawn:

1. **Enhanced Compressive Strength:** Incorporating date palm leaf fibers into Nizwa cohesive soil markedly improves its compressive strength. The study found that the strength of the soil increased by up to 85% with the addition of 2% fiber reinforcement. This substantial enhancement indicates the effectiveness of date palm leaf fibers in strengthening soil, making it a viable alternative to traditional metal and geosynthetic materials.
2. **Optimum Moisture Content:** The presence of date palm leaf fibers in the soil influences its moisture retention characteristics. As the fiber content increases, there is a corresponding increase in the optimum moisture content of the soil. This suggests that the fibers help in retaining more moisture, which could be beneficial in maintaining soil stability and workability under various environmental conditions.
3. **Maximum Dry Unit Weight:** The study observed a decrease in the maximum dry unit weight of the soil with increasing fiber content. This indicates that while the fibers enhance strength, they also reduce the soil's density. This trade-off between increased strength and decreased density needs to be considered in practical applications, as it might affect the overall stability and load-bearing capacity of the reinforced soil.

Overall, the research demonstrates that date palm leaf fibers can be effectively used as a natural reinforcement material to improve the mechanical properties of cohesive soils. The findings support further exploration and potential application of these fibers in geotechnical engineering, especially in regions where date palm leaves are abundantly available.

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